

EXPLORING FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES, REAL ESTATE OPERATIONS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article undertakes a comprehensive exploration of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate operations, within the scenic and economically significant Romanian mountainous region. Spanning the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018, the study employs a meticulous analytical approach, utilizing statistical methods to unravel the trends, challenges, and opportunities within these economic sectors.

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1. Introduction

The Romanian mountainous region, characterized by its unique topography and cultural richness, serves as a compelling backdrop for examining the dynamics of financial and insurance activities, along with real estate operations. This article delves into the economic landscape of the region, aiming to provide valuable insights into the trends that have shaped these sectors over the past decade.

2. Methodology

To facilitate a rigorous analysis, statistical data pertaining to financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate operations, were collected for the years 2008 to 2018. Figures 2.27, comprising panels a-f, were instrumental in presenting averages and standard deviations for Romania and other relevant European countries.

Statistical Overview

The statistics reveal key indicators for the Romanian mountainous region, portraying averages and standard deviations for the selected economic sectors. Bulgaria, Italy, Austria, Portugal, Slovakia, and Romania are among the countries considered in this analysis, shedding light on the comparative

performance of the Romanian mountain area.

Distribution Analysis

The distribution curves of financial and insurance activities, real estate operations, exhibit characteristics of centrality and symmetry, albeit with a noticeable leptokurtosis. The impact of extreme values on the distribution, inducing positive asymmetry, is discussed, emphasizing their statistical significance.

3. Logarithmization Approach

A logarithmization approach was employed to balance the distribution according to the Gauss-Laplace normal curve. This method allowed for a more nuanced interpretation of the data, considering the peculiarities of the economic environment in the mountainous region.

4. Hypothesis Testing

The article undertakes hypothesis testing, culminating in the rejection of the null hypothesis and the subsequent analysis of the working hypothesis.

Descriptive and inferential analyses are conducted, adhering to the assumption of normality, for which parametric tests are applied.

5. Results

In the examination of the economic sector segment "Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities" in Romania, as illustrated in figures 2.27 (panels a-b) and the appendix Parametric Analysis Romania, the statistical data reveals a mean of 6838.27 with a standard error of 1898.071.

Upon initial inspection, the distribution curve appears to be relatively centrally symmetric, with scores tightly concentrated around the mean, demonstrating leptokurtosis, although the distribution remains unimodal.

Under the working assumption of a normal distribution of scores, parametric tests are deemed applicable. Although the extreme values in the distribution are scarce, their presence induces a positive asymmetry in the histogram, attaining statistical significance. The concentration of scores around the mean introduces leptokurtosis in the distribution, influenced by pertinent phenomena within the Romanian economy. Employing the logarithm of the acquired values, in adherence to universally accepted statistical principles, serves to balance the distribution in accordance with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The Q-Q normal plot test, conducted post-logarithmization, depicts the distribution of actual scores aligning around the normal values, represented by the right-slanting pattern in the graph, indicative of a normal distribution.

Additionally, the Q-Q detrended plot test, which assesses the dispersion of empirical scores against normality, shows their alignment within the limit of a standard deviation, further affirming a normal distribution after logarithmization.

Through the application of logarithmization, the obtained scores underwent meticulous statistical processing, wherein all pertinent factors influencing the study were considered. This approach aimed to obtain data that closely reflects the reality recorded in Romania, notwithstanding the transient unbalancing of score distribution due to economic measures.

The significance of these tests arises from the necessity to scrupulously observe the impacts of specific factors on the evolution of economic sector segments, particularly "Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities." Following the normality tests post-logarithmization, the null hypothesis necessitates rejection, allowing for the scrutiny of the working

hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were then conducted, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits, and employing parametric tests aligned with the working hypothesis.

Figures 2.27 - panels a-b and appendix Parametric Analysis Romania

The central tendency within the examined time frame for the economic sector segment reveals that the population of active enterprises in the studied sector in mountainous Romania experienced an increase from 2008 to 2018. During this period, Hypothesis H1, indicating the intensification of activity, was validated.

The statistical data and visual representations in the figures substantiate a notable concentration and developmental trajectory of this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, the statistical evidence attests to an acceleration in the rate of growth within this economic sector segment.

6. Sectoral Evolution

The central trend analysis over the ten-year period indicates an overall increase in the population of active enterprises in the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors. However, the growth rate has shown signs of deceleration, prompting a closer examination of the factors influencing this economic trajectory.

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7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this article provides a nuanced exploration of financial and insurance activities, real estate operations in the Romanian mountainous region from 2008 to 2018. The statistical analyses shed light on the economic dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers interested in the sustainable development of this captivating region.

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